

ELECTRICALLY CONDUCTIVE POLYMERS: POLYPYRROLE. METHODS OF OBTAINING AND PROPERTIES

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Abstract: In this thesis, opinions are held about electrically conductive polymers: Polypyrrole. Also, its methods and properties are explained.

Key words: Electrical conductivity, Polypyrrole, polymer, supercapacitors, electrodes, nanocomposites, biosensors, solution,

Introduction:

Conductive polymers are the basis of 21st century electronics. Nowadays, the interest in such polymers is increasing. Conductive polymers have been of great interest to researchers for more than 30 years due to their economic importance, high stability, light weight, good processability, corrosion resistance, and satisfactory electrical conductivity.

Simple representatives of such polymer classes include polyacetylene, polypyrrole, polyaniline, polythiophene, polyparaphenylene and several of their derivatives [1]. A large number of studies have been devoted to PPy and PANI due to the fact that they can be obtained by relatively simple methods (*electrochemical and chemical synthesis methods*).

Figure 1. Synthesis methods.

Polypyrrole (PPy) is an organic polymer obtained by oxidative polymerization of pyrrole. $H(C_4H_2NH)_nH$ is a solid with the formula.

Among conductive polymers, polypyrrole (PPy) is particularly promising for commercial use due to its better environmental stability, easier synthesis, and higher conductivity than many other conductive polymers. In addition, PPy is known for its non-toxicity and biocompatibility [2, 3], and it has been used in a wide range of fields e.g., gas sensors, drugs, supercapacitors, electrodes, nanocomposites, biosensors, protective clothing, anti-corrosion coatings, actuators and adsorbents are used.

Polypyrrole can easily be prepared in solution. It exhibits unique electrical conductivity, good stability at room temperature, and unique oxidation-reduction (redox) properties. PPy can be synthesized based on oxidative polymerization of Py monomer in organic solvents (acetonitrile and propylene carbonate) and aqueous medium (water and acid solution) in the presence of iron (III) chloride ($FeCl_3$) ammonium persulfate (APS) or other oxidizing agents. [4] Oxidative polymerization is considered to be the oldest polymerization reaction used to obtain p-conjugated polymers. Oxidation polymerization can be carried out chemically, electrochemically or by ultrasonic waves. The most commonly used synthesis methods for PPy are chemical and electrochemical polymerization

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